

THERMAL STRESSES IN LAYERED CYLINDERS

James Ting-Shun Wang and Chien-Chang Lin
Institute of Applied Mathematics
National Chung-Hsing University
Taichung, Taiwan 40227 R.O.C.

ABSTRACT

An analysis of a cylinder consisting of a number of homogeneous layers of different materials subjected to a thermal loading is presented in this study. Each layer is treated as an individual thin elastic shell with interfacial stresses on inner and outer surfaces as the loading. The in-plane stresses are taken to vary linearly through the thickness of each layer, and the transverse stresses are determined in terms of in-plane stress parameters by solving the equilibrium equations exactly. The compatibility condition is satisfied on the average through each layer, and the continuity in displacements at interface of adjacent layers are maintained. Some numerical results are presented for illustrative purposes.

Keywords: thermal stress, thin layer, cylinder, orthotropic.

INTRODUCTION

Thick sections of shells of layered constructions are becoming important in many engineering applications. While the Kirchhoffean shell theory has been well established for thin elastic shells, various ad hoc theories accounting for effects of overall transverse shear deformation and transverse normal strain have been given by many authors. A brief discussion of previous works and concise presentation of a generalization of the Sander's theory to laminated shells can be found in [1]. These refined theories generally improve the accuracy in determining frequencies and buckling loads. It is less clear in the improvement of the accuracy of stresses. A theory established for determining interlaminar stresses by treating each thin layer as an individual thin shell with interfacial stresses as loading has been used for analyzing cylinders under surface pressures [2], and in centrifugal field [3]. While the compatibility condition is satisfied on the average through each layer, the continuity in displacement is exactly satisfied at all interfaces. All results compare well with the exact solutions, and the procedures based on the theory are effective and have no limitation to the overall thickness of the cylinders. On the basis of the same concept of the theory used in [2] and [3], an analysis for determining stresses in layered cylinders subjected to thermal loading is presented in this study.

THE THEORY

The theory is derived for a complete cylinder consisting of n -number of homogeneous layers of different materials subjected to axisymmetric thermal loading. Each layer is treated as an individual thin elastic shell of generally orthotropic material with interfacial stresses on inner and outer surfaces as the boundary loading. The in-plane stresses are taken to vary linearly through the thickness of each layer. Such stress variation motivated by the successful application of the conventional thin shell theory is believed to be accurate. Furthermore, since the analysis procedure established in the study requires literally no computation time, the thickness of each layer taken can be far within the usual thin shell limit. The transverse stresses are determined in terms of in-plane stress parameters by solving the equilibrium equations exactly, and the method of body force analogy for thermal stress analysis is followed. With the average compatibility condition satisfied through each thin layer, relations for all stress parameters of each layer are established when the traction boundary conditions are satisfied along the inner and outer surfaces of the layer. These parameters consist of in-plane stresses at the inner and outer surface locations, and the interface stresses at the inner and outer surfaces of the layer. Expressing in-plane stress parameters in terms of interface stresses and requiring continuity of displacement along each interface, recurrence relations relating interfacial stresses in adjacent interfaces are established. When the boundary conditions at the inner and outer surfaces of the complete cylinder are satisfied, the traction at one interface can be determined. All other stresses are then calculated from the recurrence relations.

The equilibrium equation for the axisymmetric stress distribution is

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + f^* = 0 \quad (1)$$

in which σ_r and σ_θ are the true normal stress components in radial r and circumferential θ directions respectively, and f^* is the body force in the radial direction. The geometry and some symbols are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Geometry

The stress-strain relations accounting for the temperature change T are

$$\sigma_r = C_{11}\epsilon_r + C_{12}\epsilon_\theta - \beta_r T \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = C_{12}\epsilon_r + C_{22}\epsilon_\theta - \beta_\theta T \quad (3)$$

in which

$$C_{11} = \frac{E_r}{\rho} \quad ; \quad C_{22} = \frac{E_\theta}{\rho} \quad ; \quad \rho = 1 - \nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r}$$

$$C_{12} \frac{E_\theta \nu_{\theta r}}{\rho} \quad ; \quad C_{21} = \frac{E_r \nu_{r\theta}}{\rho} \quad ; \quad C_{12} = C_{21}$$

$$\beta_r = C_{11}(\alpha_r + \nu_{\theta r}\alpha_\theta) \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_\theta = C_{22}(\alpha_\theta + \nu_{r\theta}\alpha_r)$$

where E_r and E_θ are moduli of elasticity in r and θ directions respectively; $\nu_{r\theta}$ and $\nu_{\theta r}$ are Poisson's ratios; and α_r and α_θ are coefficients of linear thermal expansion in r and θ directions respectively for a general j th layer. The subscript j for the layer is suspended for the convenience of discussion. Introducing fictitious stresses $\tau_{rr} = \sigma_r + \beta_r T$ and $\tau_{\theta\theta} = \sigma_\theta + \beta_\theta T$, and fictitious body force $B = f^* - \beta_r(T_{,r} + T/r) + \beta_\theta T/r$ where a letter after a comma denotes differentiation; Equation (1) becomes

$$\frac{d}{dr}(r\tau_{rr}) - \tau_{\theta\theta} + Br = 0 \quad (4)$$

The strain, displacement and fictitious stress relations are

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{du}{dr} = \frac{1}{C}(C_{22}\tau_{rr} - C_{12}\tau_{\theta\theta}) \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_\theta = \frac{u}{r} = \frac{1}{C}(C_{11}\tau_{\theta\theta} - C_{21}\tau_{rr}) \quad (6)$$

in which $C = C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}C_{21}$ and u is the displacement in the radial direction. The in-plane stress is assumed to vary linearly through the thickness of each layer in the following form:

$$\tau_{\theta\theta} = \frac{\tau_\theta^+ + \tau_\theta^-}{2} + \frac{\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^-}{h}\left(r - \frac{R^+ + R^-}{2}\right) \quad (7)$$

where superscripts - and + denote inner and outer surfaces respectively, and h is the thickness of the layer. By substituting Equation (7) into (4) and integrating the resulting equation once with respect to r , we obtain

$$\tau_{rr} = \frac{\tau_\theta^+ + \tau_\theta^-}{2} + \frac{\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^-}{2h}(r - R^+ + R^-) - F + \frac{A}{r} \quad (8)$$

in which

$$F = \frac{1}{r} \int Br dr$$

The interfacial stresses at the inner and outer surfaces of the layer at $r = R^-$ and R^+ respectively are

$$\tau_{rr} = \tau_r^- = \frac{\tau_\theta^+ + \tau_\theta^-}{2} - \frac{\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^-}{2h} R^+ - F^- + \frac{A}{R^-} \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_{rr} = \tau_r^+ = \frac{\tau_\theta^+ + \tau_\theta^-}{2} - \frac{\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^-}{2h} R^- - F^+ + \frac{A}{R^+} \quad (10)$$

Subtracting Equation (9) from Equation (10), we obtain

$$A = \left[\frac{1}{2}(\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^-) - (\tau_r^+ - \tau_r^-) - (F^+ - F^-) \right] \frac{R^+ R^-}{h} \quad (11)$$

By eliminating the integration constant A between Equations (9) and (10), we obtain

$$\tau_\theta^+ + \tau_\theta^- = \frac{2}{h} [(\tau_r^+ R^+ - \tau_r^- R^-) - (F^+ R^+ - F^- R^-)] \quad (12)$$

We next require that the compatibility equation be satisfied on the average through the thickness of the layer while the stress equilibrium condition is now satisfied exactly. By integrating the following compatibility equation between $r = R^-$ and R^+ :

$$r \frac{d\epsilon_\theta}{dr} + \epsilon_\theta - \epsilon_r = 0 \quad (13)$$

and using the stress-strain relations given in Equations (2) and (3), we obtain

$$(\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^-) [(2E_r + E_\theta K - E_\theta)] + \frac{H}{2} (E_r - E_\theta) (\tau_\theta^+ + \tau_\theta^-) K = -2E_\theta (\tau_r^+ - \tau_r^-) \quad (14)$$

in which

$$K = \frac{4H}{(4 - H^2) \ln \frac{2+H}{2-H}}$$

where $H=h/R$, and R is the radius of curvature of the mid-surface of the layer. It may be noted that since H is a small quantity, hence K is essentially equal to unity. Substitution of Equation (12) into Equation (14) results in the following equation:

$$\tau_\theta^+ - \tau_\theta^- = \zeta^+ \tau_r^+ - \zeta^- \tau_r^- + \phi^+ F^+ - \phi^- F^- \quad (15)$$

in which

$$\zeta^+ R \phi^+ = 2R^+ (E_\theta - E_r) K \quad ; \quad R^- \phi^- = R^+ \phi^-$$

$$\zeta^* \zeta^+ = \zeta^* \phi^+ - 2E_\theta \quad ; \quad \zeta^* \zeta^- = \zeta^* \phi^- - 2E_\theta$$

$$\zeta^* = (2E_r + E_\theta)K - E_\theta$$

Adding and subtracting Equations (11) and (13), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_\theta^+ &= \left(\frac{R^+}{h} + \frac{1}{2}\zeta^+\right)\tau_r^+ - \left(\frac{R^-}{h} + \frac{1}{2}\zeta^-\right)\tau_r^- \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{R^+}{h} - \frac{1}{2}\phi^+\right)F^+ + \left(\frac{R^-}{h} - \frac{1}{2}\phi^-\right)F^- \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_\theta^- &= \left(\frac{R^+}{h} - \frac{1}{2}\zeta^+\right)\tau_r^+ - \left(\frac{R^-}{h} - \frac{1}{2}\zeta^-\right)\tau_r^- \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{R^+}{h} + \frac{1}{2}\phi^+\right)F^+ + \left(\frac{R^-}{h} + \frac{1}{2}\phi^-\right)F^- \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

By using Equation (5) in conjunction with Equations (7), (8) and (11), the continuity condition in radial displacement u or simply circumferential strain ϵ_θ along each interface becomes

$$-\left(\frac{\nu_{\theta r}}{E_\theta}\right)_j p_j^+ + \left(\frac{1}{E_\theta}\right)_j \tau_{\theta j}^+ = -\left(\frac{\nu_{\theta r}}{E_\theta}\right)_{j+1} p_{j+1}^- + \left(\frac{1}{E_\theta}\right)_{j+1} \tau_{\theta j+1}^- \quad (18)$$

in which both p_j and p_{j+1} are the fictitious interfacial radial traction at the j th interface. They are generally not equal to each other. However, for certain transversely isotropic composite materials, β_r for various ply groups would be close. For simplicity of discussion, we consider that they be equal to p_j . By using Equations (16) and (17) in Equation (18), we arrive at the following recurrence relations for unknown interfacial stresses at adjacent interfaces:

$$A_{j+1} p_{j+1} = B_j p_j + C_{j-1} p_{j-1} + G_j \quad (19)$$

in which A_{j+1} , B_j , and C_{j-1} are functions of geometrical and mechanical constants, and G_j involves the temperature. If we start from inner surface, then all the fictitious interfacial tractions can be expressed in terms of the traction p_0 at the inner surface and p_1 at the outer surface through the recurrence relation given in Equation (19). This may be written in the following general form:

$$p_j = a_{j1} p_1 + a_{j0} p_0 + f_j \quad (20)$$

in which f_j is a function of F_1, F_2, \dots, F_j . Hence if the fictitious traction p_n at $r=R_n$ is given, then through the continuity condition at $(n-1)$ th interface, we arrive at

$$p_n = a_{n1} p_1 + a_{n0} p_0 + f_n \quad (21)$$

from which we can determine p_1 immediately with known p_0 and f_n .

If the cylinder under p_0 is fixed at the outer surface $r=R_n$, we require u or ϵ_θ to be zero. As a result, we have

$$\bar{A}p_n = \bar{B}p_{n-1} + \bar{C}_n \quad (22)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{A} &= \frac{1}{h_n}R_n + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_n^+ - \nu_{\theta r n} \\ \bar{B} &= \frac{1}{h_n}R_{n-1} + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_n^- \\ \bar{C}_n &= \left(\frac{1}{h_n}R_n - \frac{1}{2}\phi_n^+\right)F_n - \left(\frac{1}{h_n}R_{n-1} - \frac{1}{2}\phi_n^-\right)F_{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

Equation(22) can be expressed in terms of p_1 and p_0 by using Equation (20). Hence p_1 can be determined for given p_0 and T subsequently. On the other hand, if the cylinder under p_n is fixed along the inner surface $r = R_0$, the fixity condition leads to

$$A^*p_0 = B^*p_1 + C^* \quad (23)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} A^* &= \frac{1}{h_1}R_0 - \frac{1}{2}\zeta_1^- + \nu_{\theta r 1} \\ B^* &= \frac{1}{h_1}R_1 - \frac{1}{2}\zeta_1^+ \\ C^* &= \left(\frac{1}{h_1}R_0 - \frac{1}{2}\phi_1^-\right)F_0 - \left(\frac{1}{h_1}R_1 - \frac{1}{2}\phi_1^+\right)F_1 \end{aligned}$$

The fictitious tractions p_0 and p_1 can be determined for given p_n and T by solving Equations (21) and (23). It is seen that p_0 and p_1 can be determined when temperature variation T through the thickness and various conditions along the inner and outer surfaces of the cylinder are given. Interfacial tractions at any other interfaces can be determined from Equation (20). Once the fictitious stresses are calculated from Equations (7) and (8) in conjunction with Equations (9) through (11), (16) and (17), the true stresses are obtained by subtracting $\beta_r T$ and $\beta_\theta T$ from fictitious stresses for radial and circumferential components respectively.

EXAMPLES

In order to check the accuracy of the theory, a homogeneous isotropic cylinder under constant temperature throughout is considered. Basic theory and analysis of such problems can be found in standard textbooks involving thermoelasticity and thick cylinders such as

[4-7]. For isotropic materials, $\beta_r = \beta_\theta = \beta = E\alpha/(1-\nu)$. As the first example, a cylinder fixed at the outer surface at $r=a$ and free at the inner surface $r=b$ is analyzed for various a/b ratios ranging from 4 to 10. The cylinder is divided into 45 layers in the present theory. All results compared to exact solutions show negligible discrepancy. Results for the case $a=10b$ are given in Table 1 for illustrative purposes.

Table 1. Comparison of Results ($a=10b$)

r/b	$\sigma_r/\beta T$	$\sigma_r/\beta T$	$\sigma_\theta/\beta T$	$\sigma_\theta/\beta T$
	<i>Exact</i>	<i>Present</i>	<i>Exact</i>	<i>Present</i>
1	0	0	-1.9672	-1.9676
2	-0.7377	-0.7397	-1.2295	-1.2279
4	-0.9221	-0.9229	-1.0451	-1.0447
6	-0.9563	-0.9567	-1.0109	-1.0108
8	-0.9682	-0.9686	-0.9990	-0.9990
10	-0.9738	-0.9740	-0.9934	-0.9935

As a second example, we consider a cylinder consisting of 45 layers of alternating ply groups of 0° and 90° fibers under constant temperature distribution. The exterior layers are 90° ply groups. The fiber orientation angle is measured with reference to the longitudinal axis of the cylinder. The radius of the mid-surface of the first layer is taken to be 1 in. and the thickness of each layer is 0.01 in, so that each layer is far within the usual thin shell limitation. The mechanical properties $E_r = E_\theta = 2.2 \times 10^6$ psi and $\nu_{\theta r} = 0.21$ for 0° ply groups, and $E_r = 2.2 \times 10^6$ psi and $E_\theta = 20.2 \times 10^6$ psi and $\nu_{\theta r} = 0.21$ for 90° ply groups used in [8, 9] are used. For simplicity, we consider $\alpha_L = 0.088\alpha_T$ where α_L and α_T are coefficients of linear thermal expansion in the longitudinal and transverse directions of the fiber respectively. As a result, $\beta_r = \beta_\theta = \beta$. Some results on the stresses at interface locations for a cylinder fixed along the outer surface, $r=R_n$, and free at the inner surface $r=R_0$ is given in Table 2. Two values of σ_θ indicating stress discontinuity are shown in Table 2 at all interface locations.

Table 2. Stresses in a 45-layer cylinder

<i>InterfaceNo.</i>	$\sigma_r/\beta T$	$\sigma_\theta/\beta T$
0	0	-4.4809
1	-0.4073	-4.0736 (-1.1884)
2	-0.4724	-1.1233 (-1.8902)
3	-0.6584	-2.7042 (-1.1056)
4	-0.6904	-1.0736 (-2.1315)
5	-0.7864	-2.0354 (-1.0644)
:	:	:
:	:	:
15	-0.9588	-1.1781 (-1.0108)
25	-0.9847	-1.0522 (-1.0026)
35	-0.9914	-1.0159 (-1.0000)
45	-0.9935	-0.991

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Following the same concept of the theory developed previously by the authors, results for a homogeneous cylinder of isotropic material divided into 45 layers are used for comparing to the exact solutions. For the thickest cylinder with the outside radius being ten times the inside radius, the maximum discrepancy is within 0.3 percent. Stresses in cylinders of various thicknesses having layers of 0° and 90° ply groups of composite materials are computed. Numerical results for one case is presented for illustrative purposes. All results indicate that the method of analysis established is simple to use, and has no limitation to the total thickness of the cylinder.

Acknowledgment

Partial support from the National Science Council of the Republic of China under the research grant No. NSC82-0401-E005-015 is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. Reddy, J.N., *Energy and Variational Methods in Applied Mechanics*, New York: Wiley, 1984.
2. Wang, J.T.S., Lin, C.C., *Interface Stresses in Laminated Cylindrical Shells*, Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Composites '93, Wollongong, Australia, February 15-19, 1993.
3. Wang, J.T.S., Lin, C.C., *Stresses in Rotating Composite Cylindrical Shells*, Special Issue of the Journal of Composite Structures for the Seventh International Conference on Composite Structures, Paisley, Scotland, July 5-7, 1993.
4. Boley, B.A., Weiner, J.H., *Theory of Thermal Stresses*, New York: Wiley, 1960.
5. Timoshenko, S., Goodier, J.N., *Theory of Elasticity*, 2nd ed. New York: McGraw Hill, 1951.
6. Wang, C.T., *Applied Elasticity*, New York: McGraw Hill, 1953.
7. Gould, P.L., *Introduction to Linear Elasticity*, New York: Springer-Verlag, 1983.
8. Wang, A.S.D., Crossman, F.W., *Some New Results on Edge Effect in Symmetric Laminates*, Journal of Composite Materials, 11, 1977, pp. 92-106.
9. Wang, J.T.S., Dickson, J.N., *Interlaminar Stresses in Symmetric Composite Laminates*, Journal of Composite Materials, 12, 1978, pp. 390-402.